

GHOST: High-Resolution Optical Spectroscopy at Gemini South

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GHOST, the Gemini High-resolution Optical SpecTrograph, is the latest facility instrument at Gemini South, part of the International Gemini Observatory. GHOST delivers advanced high-resolution spectroscopic capabilities with broad simultaneous wavelength coverage and high throughput. This new instrument empowers astronomers to answer a variety of scientific questions, such as studying the intergalactic medium using observations of quasars, how the Universe evolved by observations of very old metal-poor stars, and identifying and characterizing exoplanetary systems.

This sophisticated instrument comprises three key elements: a Cassegrain unit mounted on the telescope, a spectrograph bench housed in a highly stable enclosure at the pier lab, and a fiber cable connecting the two. The on-telescope Cassegrain unit encompasses the positioning system for the object and sky fiber Integral Field Units (IFUs), with each object IFU incorporating mini-ADCs (atmospheric dispersion correctors). Interested users should consult the GHOST web pages for further details.

The GHOST [System Verification \(SV\)](#) was successfully carried out on 9–17 May, and it was allocated a 40-hour time block at Gemini South. Most of the high-priority observations across the various programs were completed during this timeframe. Raw data from the SV run is now accessible in the [public Gemini Observatory Archive](#). For comprehensive details regarding the conducted observations during the SV run and ongoing data evaluations, please refer to the [GHOST science web page](#). Moreover, the reduced data is also currently accessible in the archive. The SV team, composed of Gemini observatory personnel and community representatives, planned, conducted, reduced, and evaluated the SV observations. A subset of this group, the Instrument Science Team (IST), was primarily responsible for developing observations for SV and reducing and analyzing those datasets. The IST was chosen in consultation with the Gemini Directorate, Science and Technology Advisory Committee (STAC), and the National Research Council (NRC)-led GHOST instrument team.

To foster community engagement and share outcomes from the SV process, a series of GHOST webinars took place in late July / early August 2023. Additional information can be found on the [GHOST Webinar Series web page](#).

The dedicated [GHOST Shared Risk Call for Proposals](#) through the Fast Turnaround program has been successfully concluded. The anticipated GHOST observation block was scheduled from 30 November to 19 December. The 15 submitted proposals included 10 from the US, 3 from Canada, 1 from Brazil, and 1 from South Korea, collectively requesting 71.37 hours. Out of these, 14 proposals were accepted (9 from the US, 3 from Canada, 1 from Brazil, and 1 from South Korea), with a total grant time of 51.47 hours (49.22 hours for Band 1 and 2; 2.25 hours for Band 3). 80% of the time allocated was observed. All B1 and B3 programs were completed, with 8 out of 10 Band 2 programs also completed.

GHOST was offered fully in the 24A Call for Proposals. Based on preliminary information, the requested time for GHOST appears to be close to 20% of the total requested time at Gemini South.

Early Scientific Results Using GHOST SV Data

During the GHOST System Verification, data were taken of a chemically peculiar star in the halo of the Milky Way. The analysis of these data was recently published in Placco et al. (2023). The object, SPLUS J142445.34–254247.1, was first observed in 2019 with GMOS at Gemini South. Observations confirmed its low iron content, and it was selected as a potential target for high-resolution follow-up. The GHOST data, taken with the standard resolution mode ($R \sim 50,000$), allowed for the determination of chemical abundances for 36 elements from the periodic table, from carbon to thorium. With an iron abundance about 2500 lower than the Sun, SPLUS J1424–2542 is one of the lowest metallicity stars with measured thorium. It also has the highest thorium-to-europium ratio observed to date, making it part of the “actinide-boost” category. Such stars can help constrain the operation of the rapid neutron-capture process (r-process) in the early Universe.

The analysis suggests that the gas cloud from which SPLUS J1424–2542 was formed must have been enriched by at least two events. The light-element ($Z \leq 30$) abundance pattern is consistent with the yields from a supernova explosion of metal-free stars with 11–13 solar masses, and the heavy-element ($Z \geq 38$) abundance pattern can be reproduced by the yields from a neutron star merger event. An analysis of

how the star is moving across the Milky Way also reveals that SPLUS J1424–2542 is a low-mass, old halo star with a likely in situ origin, not associated with any known early merger events in the Milky Way.

Reference

Placco, V. M., et al. 2023, *ApJ*, 959, 60

Sections of the GHOST spectrum of SPLUS J1424–2542 showing selected absorption features used for chemical abundance determinations